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ROLE OF RELIGION IN THE ISRAEL–PALESTINE CONFLICT

Olayinka Olanrewaju

Obafemi Awolowo University, Nigeria

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Abstract: The role of religion in politics has been a major historical factor in the world for several decades, raising significant questions about whether religion functions as a catalyst for conflict or peace. This thesis focuses specifically on the role of religion in the Israeli-Palestinian conflict from the perspective of Judaism and Islam tenets and the manner in which actors incorporate religion into their national politics. The research is based on a case study and uses qualitative data to analyze academic literature and work. The research concludes that the Israel–Palestine conflict is not about religion but was influenced by religion to a large extent.

Keywords: Religion, Islam, Judaism, Zionism, Israeli-Palestinian conflict, religious Zionism

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background of the Study

The Palestinian-Israeli conflict is considered one of the most intractable conflicts in world history that seems to defy conflict resolution processes and international mediation (Albin, 1997; Gabbay, 2007). Not only is the conflict unsolvable, but it is also deteriorating and escalating as the positions and willingness of both parties to embrace peace become more polarized. The political discussions on both sides of the Israeli-Palestinian conflict are infused with religious connotations, values, and symbols that prioritize the sanctity of the land under dispute. Therefore, in this research, we shall examine the national policies toward the Arab–Israeli conflict to evaluate how religious belief has and continues to shape policymakers' decisions.

The issue of land encompasses many different issues, such as Jerusalem's future, the solution to the refugees' question, the final border between Palestinians and Israelis, and the settlements in the West Bank and Gaza Strip. Despite the Oslo Declaration of Principles of 1993, the parties of the conflict preferred to preserve the idea of the continuation of the conflict as an instrument for insisting on their national demands. This culminated in a deadlock in the peace efforts, which mainly failed in bringing forward the offers of peaceful solutions regarding sharing the same territory. The ambition of the Jews to settle on the strategic parts of Palestine and ensure its borders and the Palestinians' efforts to regain their territories from the Israelis led to the failure in achieving territorial compromise in every peace effort. This thesis emphasizes the failure of every peace effort to prove the importance of territorial compromise once again for the settlement of the Arab-Israeli conflict. The military and political conflicts between Israel and some Arab countries have lasted for decades, causing numerous casualties, economic loss, and regional turmoil.

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1.2 Statement of the problem

It is important to identify and analyze the underlying reasons for solving the situation in this region. The conflicts and disputes between Palestine and Israel caused by territorial issues are important reasons that cannot be ignored. However, it is often overlooked whether the religious reason is also an important factor in conflicts. Theologians, historians, and social scientists have all delved into the question of religion in Palestine, yielding several theories regarding its nature, origin, and historical significance. They have explored their relationship with various competing groups in the region, including their rituals, traditions, and cultural or political reflections (e.g., Mollov and Lavie, 2001; Abu-Nimer, 2004; Moore and Guy, 2012). Moreover, each discipline or tradition brings its own focus areas and interests to the study of religion, resulting in diverse observations and interpretations.

However, academic research on related topics is lacking. Regarding religious topics, most articles are analyzed in conjunction with the news, lacking all aspects of discussion. As the holy places of Judaism and Islam, the Palestine region and Jerusalem have special religious significance. Whether religion also influences other fields, such as politics, still needs to be explored. Therefore, this article analyzes the extent to which religion has an impact on Arab-Israeli conflicts, later political negotiations, and the political arena of Palestine and Israel.

Three major areas of interest will be elaborated in this thesis. First, the research focuses on the interpretation of Judaism and Islam for land sovereignty and violence. If the tenets of both religions indicate the attributes of the land or support the use of violence to regain lost land, it will inevitably lead to conflicts and violence to a certain extent. Second, the status and influence of Israeli religious parties in the Israeli political arena will be analyzed. Israeli religious parties are practitioners of Judaism. The strength of religious parties will inevitably lead to their influence on Israel's foreign policy toward Palestine and the stagnation of the land for the peace plan. Finally, the relationship between the Palestinian organizations and Islam will be analyzed. Whether these organizations use Islamic tenets to justify violence is the key to proving the connection between religion and the Arab-Israeli conflict.

1.3 Objectives of the study

This study aims to examine the role of religion in the Israel–Palestine conflict. Associated objectives include the following:

1. To review existing academic literature and documents related to the conflict between Israel and Palestine.
2. To evaluate the extent to which the religion factor influence both Palestine and Israel.
3. To investigate other factors that contribute to the insoluble nature of the conflict.

1.4 Research Questions

The following research questions, which agree with the objectives, will be answered in this study:

1. Does religion play any role whatsoever in the conflict between Israel and Palestine?
2. What other factors promote the Israel–Palestine conflict?

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Religion or Nationalism

From the 1990s onwards, literature addressing the relationship between religion and conflicts started to emerge with several viewpoints. In this context, Samuel Huntington's hypothesis of the 'clash of civilizations'

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(Huntington, 1993) is central to the debate. Huntington posited that people's cultural and religious identities will be the main source of conflict in the post-Cold War world, although nation states will remain. Future wars would not be fought between countries but between cultures. Moreover, Huntington observed that the greatest threat to world peace was Islamic extremism, whereby major world conflicts would be drawn between the Islamic and non-Islamic worlds (Huntington 1993: 22-49).

Understanding the role of religion in the Israeli-Palestinian conflict requires an understanding of the broader ethnocentric nationalist conflict between the two sides. The latter provides the context for researching the various ways in which adherents of the Jewish and Muslim religions approach the function of their religion in the conflict. Nationalism and its ethnocentric approach to statehood is a central driver in the history of the Israeli-Palestinian conflict. However, nationalism is not unique to either the Israeli or the Palestinian side, as it is a master narrative associated with the historical development of modernity and the advent of nation-states (Alter, 1994; Anastasiou, 2008; Anderson, 1995; Gellner, 1983; Hobsbawm, 1990).

Nationalism operates under the assumption that the structure of identity is exclusively and fundamentally mono-ethnic and one-dimensional. Ignatieff (1999), a renowned scholar of ethnocentric nationalism, explains that: "As a cultural ideal, nationalism is the claim that while men and women have many identities, it is the nation that provides them with their primary form of belonging" (p. 5). Ignatieff further notes that nationalism is the most powerful mobilizer and legitimizer of deadly violence and the use of deadly force. He also asserts that nationalism provides a narrative that can readily resort to justifications for violence, unlike other references of identity and belonging, such as family or profession. It is not obvious "why national identity should be a more important element of personal identity than any other; nor is it obvious why defense of the nation justifies the use of violence" (p. 6). The implication is that unlike other aspects of identity, nationalism interprets national identity as supreme and sacred and thus worth human sacrifice. Looking at the wars and violence that have engulfed the Middle East in the post-9/11 era, one observes the intensification of competing nationalisms within as well as between societies in the broader context of the unfolding Israeli-Palestinian conflict. The relapse of nationalism in the region, and more specifically the rise of religious nationalism and militancy, have posed new challenges, especially in confrontation with, and at times in alliance with, militant transnational jihadism.

When specifically discussing the Israel-Palestine conflict, identity conflicts revolve around the groups' national identity configurations. Rothman (2001) asserts that identity-based conflicts contain primary elements that are based on mutual rejections of the legitimacy of the other side out of fear that such recognition will undermine one's own legitimacy, values, and claims. Rothman (2001) continues by saying that in the not so distant past, Israelis feared that if Palestinian claims were legitimate or taken seriously, they would undermine Israeli claims. The Palestinians had the same fears about the Israelis. Thus, the situation and concession over resources and territory were viewed as zero-sum, primarily because of fears and mutual suspicion regarding identity recognition.

2.2 Religion and Nationalism in the Israeli– Palestine Conflict

Previous studies on the Arab-Israeli conflict have mainly focused on combining facts and events to determine whether religion impacts the conflict. For instance, Sabrina (2002) analyzed the impact of religious concepts through specific events in the West Bank (Sabrina, 2002.) Anshel also explained that the Arab-Israeli conflict is

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not only a struggle over land but also a struggle based on religion (Anshel, 2014). Although the discussion of these two researchers involved religion, they did not conduct a multidimensional analysis based on this topic. Besides, the work published by them is full of subjective personal analysis without objective evaluations of the extent to which religion influences Palestine and Israel.

Researchers such as David, Benjamin, Hofman, and Aryeh believe that religion is an important factor in the Arab-Israeli conflict (David, 2008). Hofman (1970) specifically contends that both sides use religious ideology, which motivates conflict and justifies violence, for political and military purposes (Hofman, 1970). For Benjamin, Israelis are reluctant to withdraw from occupied territories because of religious considerations (Benjamin, 1973). As a result, they conclude that the Arab-Israeli conflict is more of a religious war than a territorial conflict.

On the other hand, Yuli Tamir, who does not deny that religion is a determining component in the conflict, does not believe that it is as important as it is assumed. She believes that the Arab-Israeli conflict is based on secular nationalism (Yuli, 2010). However, the influence of religion on the Arab-Israeli conflict can be, to a certain extent, polarized rather than drawn by the above scholars.

Auerbach (2011) maintains that the Israel-Palestine conflict is a conflict over real material assets, such as territory, water, border, and security. In connection to the Israeli-Palestinian conflict being a conflict over identity, Auerbach also adds that this conflict is one in which each side sees the other side's national identity as a threat, or as translating this identity into the political sphere—that is, into a “nation-state”—as a danger to its independent national identity. Auerbach continues by saying that the one side therefore rejects the definition of the other side as a nation or, at a minimum, denies its right to realize this identity in the context of national statehood. The Israeli-Palestinian conflict is, in essence, a conflict over identity because its origin and the cause of its continuation are rooted in each side's denial of the other's nationhood and each side's claim to the right to establish its own ethnocentric nation-state (p. 100). The role and function of religion is contextualized within the abovementioned framework of Israeli-Palestinian nationalist conflict, so naturally, the religion of the two sides assumes a certain relationship to nationalism.

Juergensmeyer (1996) is one of the important scholars that addresses the relationship between religion and nationalism. In his work *The Worldwide Rise of Religious Nationalism*, he focuses on the ascendancy of religious nationalism around the world, especially in the Middle East and in the Israeli-Palestinian conflict, a trend that has intensified during the post-9/11 era. Juergensmeyer indicates that there are two main kinds of religious nationalists: ethnic and ideological. Ethnic religious nationalists attack rival ethnicities, while ideological religious nationalists attack the secularity within their own country (government and supporters) or rival religions. He further states that, “If the ethnic approach to religious nationalism politicizes religion by employing religious identities for political ends, an ideological approach to religious nationalism does the opposite: it religionizes politics.” This is essential because it notes the two basic ways in which religion is integrated into national politics and national identity formations.

3. MATERIALS AND METHOD

This research paper uses a case study as the research method, giving a detailed study of the research question on the role of religion in the conflict between Israel and Palestine. This method is chosen to specifically focus on the

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case of the Arab-Israeli conflict. When elaborating the topic with a case study research design, qualitative data were collected, focusing on historical and analytical structure. This kind of research method can best analyze the given questions in the paper and best evaluate the field and extent to which religion affects Israel and Palestine. Furthermore, this thesis is mainly based on the existing literature to provide practical evidence and specific data. The primary and secondary sources will be analyzed to achieve a clearer perspective. Qualitative data collection method using books, news articles, reports, government documents, and other literature to collect relevant information to support subsequent analysis. The literature will be selected according to the topic's relevance. Secondary sources are given preference due to their specialty and sufficient analysis, for example, academic literature recognized by academia. The online academic literature was gathered from JSTOR, Masaryk University's online archive, ResearchGate, Google Scholar, Library Genesis, and Palestine-Israel Journal.

4. RESULTS AND FINDINGS

4.1 Historical Background of the Israeli– Palestine Conflict

Palestine is located in western Asia, with Lebanon to the north, the Golan Heights in Syria to the northeast, Jordan to the east, and the Sinai Peninsula in Egypt to the southwest. Being the birthplace of three major religions, namely, Judaism, Christianity, and Islam, Palestine has prominent religious significance. In ancient times, Palestine was called Canaan, and both Jews and Palestinians once settled there. Abraham, the ancestor of the Jewish people, once settled in Palestine, but his descendants were conquered by the Assyrian Kingdom, New Babylon, Persia, Macedonia, and the Roman Empire. (Nur, 2020) The Jews were forced to leave Palestine and began the global diaspora. Over time, the Arab Empire rose and conquered Palestine. The Jewish diaspora did not forget Palestine. The Zionist movement emerged at the end of the 19th century under the leadership of Theodor Herzl. Along with Zionism's proposal to return to Palestine to establish a state, Jews around the world began immigrating to Palestine.

Palestine was no longer ruled by the Ottoman Empire after the First World War. As the mandate of Palestine, the United Kingdom divided the land into Jordan in the east and Palestine in the west. The Balfour Declaration was issued by the British government to eliminate the Jewish problem in Europe and allow Jews to build homes in Palestine. (Rashid, 2020) During the Second World War, European Jews suffered persecution, and the idea of establishing their own country became increasingly strong. In 1947, the UN passed Resolution 181 on the Partition of Palestine to establish Arab and Jewish states. The resolution stipulates that 57% of Palestine's total area will be allocated to Jews, and the remaining 43% will be owned by Arabs. (Rashid, 2020) However, the Arab population in Palestine is much larger than that in Israel. Therefore, the Palestinian Arabs and Arab countries did not accept the resolution and the establishment of the State of Israel. From then on, the war between the two sides began. Since Israel's establishment, a series of conflicts and wars have broken out between Arab countries and Israel. In the early morning of the day after Israel announced its founding on May 14, 1948, Jordan, Iraq, Syria, Egypt, and other Arab countries sent troops to attack Israel. (Daniel, 2016)

The second Middle East war was a war for the Suez Canal. Egypt broke out in a war with Britain, France, and Israel. During the third Middle East war in 1967, Israel launched attacks on Egypt, Syria, and Jordan, occupied the Sinai Peninsula and the Golan Heights, and forced many Palestinians to live in the surrounding Arab countries

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and other regions (Mark, 2009). In the Fourth War of 1973, Israel fought Egypt and Syria, but both sides suffered heavy losses. After the war, Israel and Egypt signed the Camp David agreement, which finally normalized political relations. Egypt became the first Arab country to officially recognize Israel. The Palestinians have never stopped resisting Israel since its founding. Moreover, they advocate the establishment of an independent Palestinian state. In 1988, Palestine announced the establishment of a Palestinian state with Jerusalem as its capital. According to the agreement reached between Palestine and Israel, Palestine exercises limited autonomy in Gaza. Previously, the PLO refused to recognize Israel, reconcile with it, or negotiate with it and aimed to eliminate it by armed forces. It was not until the Oslo Agreement of 1993 that the PLO recognized Israel and began the peace process (Ian, 2019). Since then, peace negotiations and violent conflicts between the two sides have been intertwined.

Under the international community's mediation, the Israeli government has signed several peace agreements. However, there is always a divergence between the two sides due to Jerusalem's ownership, the issue of Jewish settlements, and the demarcation of borders. Palestine and Israel have not yet reached a permanent peace agreement. In 1967, Israel built settlements for Jewish immigrants in the occupied territories and was reluctant to withdraw from the territories occupied in 1967. In 2006, the Palestinian Islamic Resistance Movement Hamas won the election of the Palestinian Legislative Council. Israel stated that Hamas is a terrorist organization and that its government is a terrorist regime. Israel will not engage with the Palestinian government unless Hamas gives up violence, disarms and recognizes Israel, and promises to abide by the Israeli-Palestinian agreement. Other militant groups in Palestine, such as the Islamic Jihad in Palestine, still do not recognize Israel, calling on Muslims to wage a holy war against Israel and claiming that Palestine can only be liberated if Israel is eliminated.

4.2 The Israeli-Palestinian conflict: a religious or political conflict?

Two different perspectives lie at the basis of any analysis and interpretation of the origins of the Israeli-Palestinian conflict: a religious and a political one. The latter perspective perceives the conflict as a nationalist struggle that mainly consists of security, sovereignty, and self-determination. This approach divides diverse interpretations into two approaches: "The old approach sees the conflict as one raging between two national movements with an equal claim for the country and equal blame for the lack of progress, the new ones frame the conflict as one raging between a settler and a native community" (Pappé 2015) and view the conflict through the lens of settler colonialism studies. The old approach focuses on the Six-Day War of 1967 and the occupation of the West Bank and the Gaza Strip as the beginning of the conflict, whereas the new approach focuses on the 1948 ethnic cleansing of Palestine in 1948 as both a departure point and a subject that must be addressed to achieve peace and reconciliation. In addition, the old approach advocates a two-state solution. In contrast, the new one seeks a one-state solution and prefers to focus on decolonization, regime change, and refugees' return as means of reconciliation (Ibid.).

In contrast, advocates of the religious approach base their argumentation on the fact that the region that is today Israel and Palestine is holy to the three monotheistic world religions, namely, Judaism, Islam, and Christianity. They focus on Judaism and Islam and see religious motives as the origins of the conflict, often without considering the political history of Israel and Palestine. Speaking for Judaism and Christianity, the fact that a

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significant part of Judaic ritual and teachings specifically focusses on the region that is nowadays Israel and Palestine forms the basic argument for this religious approach to the conflict. In addition, the religious dimension of the conflict can also be observed in political contexts: the primary national founder of the State of Israel and the first Prime Minister of the country Ben-Gurion stated, when speaking to the Peel Commission in 1936, that “the British mandate is not our mandate,” but rather “the bible is our mandate” (Abulof 2014: 524). One year later, he disclosed, “I told the Commission: God has promised Eretz Israel to the Jews.” This is our charter. But we are men of our own time, with limited horizons” (Ibid: 525).

In addition, the employment of religious symbols by the Zionists indicates a clear reference to ancient Israel of biblical times, regardless of the fact that Zionism emerged as a predominantly secular and political movement. Furthermore, Jewish settlers who immigrated to Israel after the Six-Day War in 1967 were largely religiously motivated, as Israel’s victory gave rise to a more religious concept of Eretz Israel. As will be shown in the analysis in a more detailed way, religion and religious efforts have also had a significant impact on the course of the conflict. On both sides of the conflict, the injection of religion in the form of radical groups on the ground rejecting compromise and dialogue for religious reasons can be observed. The initial response of the Palestinians after the Arab defeat of 1948 and 1967 was secularist and political. The 1948 Palestinian exodus led to the expulsion of almost 800,000 Palestinians (Pappé 2007). His historical analysis shows that the expulsion did not happen on an ad hoc basis, but constituted a systematic ethnic cleansing in accordance with several official plans, namely, the Plan Dalet (Plan D), which was devised by the Jewish paramilitary organization Haganah in Mandatory Palestine in March 1948. The plan’s execution meant the destruction of 531 villages and 11 urban centers as well as several massacres (Ibid: 11). Because of this ethnic cleansing before the official establishment of Israel, the newly founded Israel managed to reduce the Palestinian population to under 20% of the total population (Ibid: 372). Since the ethnic cleansing of Palestine and the ongoing colonization of Palestine, the struggle of the Palestinians has mainly concerned the status of the refugees and the right to return to their homes or compensation.

However, the influence of the Muslim Brotherhood in Egypt, the successful attacks by Hezbollah in southern Lebanon against Israel, the growth of Jewish extremism expressed by the rise of power of the Israeli right (Likud party) in 1977, the Iranian Revolution in 1979, and the corruption and inefficiency of the PA provoked the search for alternatives to secularism in Palestine (Abusada 2010). The Islamic Resistance Movement (Hamas), a Palestinian Sunni-Islamic fundamentalist organization founded in 1987 by Sheik Ahmed Yassin (among others), interpreted the Palestinian tragedy in religious-political terms, believing that “Palestinians would only shake off Israeli rule when they return to Islam.” (Milton-Edwards 1996: 184-185). Its military wing, the Al-Qassam Brigades, was founded in the midst of the first Palestinian Intifada (1987-1994) against the Zionist occupation to contribute to the liberation of Palestine and the restoration of the rights of the Palestinian people under the sacred Islamic teachings of the Holy Quran, the Sunna (traditions) of Prophet Mohammad (peace and blessings of Allah be upon him), and the traditions of Muslim rulers and scholars noted for their piety and dedication (Ezzedeem Al-Qassam Brigades Information Office, s.a.). Still, this religious discourse holds a nationalist position of Hamas, namely, the political goals of stopping the Israeli occupation of Palestine, establishing a Palestinian state, and a solution to the refugee problem.

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The Hamas movement was established by the Muslim Brotherhood in December 1987 as the political wing and represents Palestinian Political Islam. A detailed description of Hamas's ideological and political development since its creation would go beyond this chapter's scope. However, it is important to note its deradicalization process during the Oslo period (1993-2000) before the outbreak of the second Intifada in September 2000, which meant the shift toward socio-political activities as a form of struggle against the occupier. As a form of protection, the building of an Islamic value system and the reestablishment of military and political power were required. Hamas gained popularity among Palestinians as it became an efficient part of the Palestinian social welfare system, providing services that the PA was unable to provide, as well as a vocal and institutionalized part of the Palestinian political landscape.

In this sense, Hamas' ideology can be characterized as an "organic interconnection between social and political action" (Roy 2003: 15). However, the outbreak of the second Intifada in 2000 reversed the process of deradicalization within the Islamic movement, which resulted from the increasing brutality of the occupiers against the Palestinian society and economy, even though the social core of the Islamic movement remains strong (Ibid.). Unlike Fatah or Hamas, the PIJ is a Palestinian nationalist organization that does not participate in the political process and seeks to re-establish a sovereign Islamic Palestinian state with the geographic borders of the pre-1948 mandate Palestine, sanctifying the land due to its historical significance to Islam. The highly secretive organization operates underground and receives limited popular support, as it violently opposes Israel's existence, mostly by performing suicide bombings (Fletcher 2008). In addition, according to general interpretations of the Quran, Muslims in general are required to not give up any land that was Muslim in the past and was part of dar al Islam and to defend land, if necessary, by force against non-believers and enemies (Khoury 1980: 130-180).

5. DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

In a brief examination of the multifaceted relationship between religion, conflict, and a potential basis for peace building in the Israeli-Palestinian context, it is clear that religion acts both as a catalyst for conflict and as a potential avenue for peace. The intricate interplay between religion, politics, historical narratives, and geopolitical aspirations also underscores the reasons behind the Israeli-Palestinian conflict. A critical insight that emerges from this analysis is that understanding the dynamics of the conflict necessitates a well-developed non-westernized social scientific approach to religion.

This approach must integrate diverse perspectives from sociology, anthropology, and political science to fully capture how sociopolitical factors shape and shape religious beliefs and practices. Such a comprehensive analytical framework is essential for addressing the complexities of religious dynamics in conflicts and for developing effective strategies for conflict resolution and mutual understanding in deeply entrenched sociopolitical disputes, such as the Israeli-Palestinian conflict. Only by adopting a social scientific lens can scholars interested in religion delve into the nuanced ways in which religion and religious issues influence the identity, perceptions, and actions of individuals and communities on both sides of the Israeli-Palestinian conflict. For instance, on the Palestinian side, groups like Hamas draw on Islamic ideology to justify their militant actions, while on the Israeli side, religious settlers in Gaza invoke Jewish religious identity to legitimize their territorial claims. Therefore, to put it simply, it is the social scientific approach that allows for a deeper exploration of how

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religious beliefs, rituals, and practices intersect with political, social, and economic factors to shape the conflict along with an adverse social and political landscape.

However, unlike what many Jews and Arabs believe, this blurring of the lines between ethnicity and faith is not unique to Judaism, though irrational to the rational mind. The fact that most of the world's religions are, to varying degrees, hereditary underlines that belonging to them is related not only to faith but also to parentage. In addition, the notion of religion as a "nation" is not alien to other religions. In Islam, it is called "umma." In my view, the religion-ethnicity pendulum tends to swing more toward the ethnic when a given religious group is a minority or feels threatened. This was the case in South Asia. A year before Israel was established, Pakistan was carved out of India. Muhammad Ali Jinnah, the country's main founding father, was a staunch atheist who saw Islam in ethno-nationalist terms.

Zionism's political leaders were not afraid to use religious symbolism and religious authorities to push their secular agenda. Herzl abandoned his pragmatic willingness to establish a Jewish state in any place, including in Uganda, in favor of Palestine because of its religious-historical importance to Jews. In addition, Herzl forged alliances of convenience with William Hechler and other Christian Zionists, which left a bad taste in his mouth. "Hechler declares my movement to be a 'Biblical' one, even though I proceed rationally in all points," Herzl confided to his diary. Similarly, secular Palestinian leaders resorted to Islamic and, to a lesser extent, Christian religious imagery and discourse to resist Zionist expansionism and appeal for wider support. This is visible in the adoption of the Dome of the Rock as a poignant symbol of the cause. Other examples include using the religiously loaded term "Fedayeen," which literally means "those who sacrifice [for God]," to describe Palestinian fighters, and Yasser Arafat's choice to call his movement Fatah (a reverse acronym of the Palestine Liberation Movement), which also means the early Islamic conquests in Arabic. That being said, this is not a unique phenomenon. Whether oppressed or oppressor, conquered or conqueror, people tend to employ at least some religious discourse to justify or resist dominance, and nationalism itself is raised to a pseudo-religion where it does not. However, over the decades, a parallel process has been occurring among each side. In this regard, the 1967 war was a pivotal moment, the "miracle" of which brought religious Zionism out of the margins and into center stage. The crushing defeat dealt a fatal blow to secular, revolutionary Arab nationalism, from which it has not recovered. Islamists have gradually filled the void. This reflects how the religious aspect of the conflict is a civil conflict within each society, sometimes more so than between the two sides, a battle for the soul of both nations. Despite religious fundamentalists' growing zealotry, the secular foundations of this conflict remain: land, resources, rights, and dignity. However, as the situations in Syria, Iraq, and Yemen show, repeating the mantra of holy war enough can make it a self-fulfilling prophecy. This unholy outcome must be avoided in the Holy Land.

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